

Relationship of Social Security Code with Platform and Gig Workers in India

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Abstract

There are varied factors of development for one country, one of the important being the labor force which makes the chain of production functional in an economy. As the economy evolved it created two diversions, namely, organized and unorganized sector. Furthermore, India sailing as a developing country, has an abundance of labor force due to large population. ILO was the first organization to dive into the labor issues and the betterment of the conditions in which labors are exposed. Moreover, the most chaotic area that required legal aid and support came out to be the unorganized sector, where more population is employed as compared to the organized sector due to the high skill requirement in those areas. The contributions of the unorganized sector to the national income are very substantial as compared to that of the organized sector. It sums more than 60% to the national income while the contribution of the organized sector is almost half of that directly depending on the industry.

Therefore, in order to facilitate the proper functioning of unorganized sector, the Unorganized Sector Worker's Social Security Act was passed in 2008, as a result of stringent protest and campaigns that was done for this sector. In India, only about 8% of workers actually get the benefits available under various labour laws, whereas, the rest of the population works in the unorganized sector, and either are not eligible for coverage, or these Acts are just not implemented for them, with the conclusion that these workers have variable employments and low incomes. In addition to this, they have no coverage of social security and have to spend out of their meager incomes for all substantial necessities such as illness and children's education and in their old age they are unable to secure viable facilities. But, in the year 2020, the labour codes were introduced, one of them being the Social Security Code which combined the various Acts and further aids the unorganised sector.

The paper throws light upon the labour laws and unorganised sector and studies the proportional relationship between the two and questions how the laws provide security to the workers in the unorganised sector with special focus on Platform and Gig workers.

Keywords: National Income, Social Security Code, Unorganised Sector Worker's Social Security Act, ILO, Organised Sector, Platform and Gig workers.

Introduction

The labour in India is divided between two categories, namely, the organised sector and the unorganised sector according to which their rights are being governed. There were ample number of laws that were introduced for protection of rights of platform and gig workers and all these laws were collected in a particular Code, known as Social Security Code in 2020. Gig workers were introduced for the first time in this Code and defines such workers as the person performs in the work or participates in the work arrangement, which is certainly out of employer-employee relationship. Similarly, the platform workers are those who earn money by performing certain tasks on the specific platforms such as the sites like Amazon and Flipkart, etc., as per the definition of the Code.

Moreover, from the time labour laws came into existence, this issue was always vulnerable for the prospects of unorganised sector. Before the commencement of this Code, the area of social security of the workers engaged in the unorganised sector were covered by various legislations, which caused confusion and ambiguity with respect to the rights and duties of the workers. The Code again provides for the income and health security of the workers and to ensure that the schemes and benefits reach the targeted mass.

The Code vests special rights to the Central and State governments to frame schemes and policies for widening the social security of workers and it can be funded by both the governments together or from corporate social responsibility. There is also a direction given to the Central government to constitute a National Social Security Board for these group of workers, in order to monitor the proper functioning and implementation of the schemes initiated for the welfare purposes.

Salient Features of the Social Security Code

The Social Security Code is the widest Code among the four, which talks about security net to be made available to all the workers, irrespective of the fact that whether the worker belongs to the organised sector or unorganised sector. Furthermore, for the Code to be applicable to the establishments which are registered through the provisions provided under the Code and as prescribed by Central government. In addition to this, the provision for Employees Provident Fund is applicable to all establishments provided that it should have minimum threshold of 20 workers and minimum 10% of contribution is required to be made by both employee as well as the employer. The funds are to be used for the purposes of medical treatment and attendance, at the same time, payment of fees to the members of Corporation and Committees.

The provision of Gratuity is also introduced through this Code, where every establishment or shop should have at least 10 workers or more on any day preceding twelve months of the year, provided it should be notified to the appropriate government from time to time. But it is important to note that the period of employment should be continuous five years so as to claim the benefits of this provision, unless the termination of the employment is due to death, disablement or expiration of the fixed term of employment.

If we dive more into the provisions of the Code, we find the provision of maternity benefits to be bestowed to the female workers employed in the factory, mine or plantation or any other establishments under the Government or every shop, where there are 10 or more than 10 workers employed on any day from preceding twelve months or which are notified by the appropriate government. It ensures that the maternity leave is to be provided for maximum 26 weeks and it should not precede by 8 weeks from the delivery date.

In order to substantiate, there are other benefits as well which are provided by the Code to the employees such as cess and social security with respect to the workers employed at construction sites, compensation and most importantly, the information regarding employment and vacancies, at the same time, to monitor the flow of employment opportunities with the establishment of "Career Centres" in order to provide and regulate the employment facilities and grievances related to the employment process. Therefore, it is made mandatory to notify on the appropriate websites, if at all, there is any vacancy in any sector of employment.

Vulnerability Of Unorganised Sector

Whenever the term of unorganised sector was discussed by various Commissions and Committees, the problem that was faced by them most of the time was giving a proper structure and to identify the boundary or ambit of the sector. Whenever the question of defining the term came into existence, then it was always opined that everything which falls outside the purview of organised sector is deemed to be unorganised sector. But in order to frame the laws to provide maximum support to the workers as well as to implement the provisions of Directive Principles of State Policy, it is important to identify the areas which constitute the unorganised sector where majority of workforce in India is employed with minimum or no employment security and are devoid from the availability of rights to which they are entitled to receive from their respective employer.

The term "organised" is generally used to refer those employment places where 10 or more than 10 workers are employed in order to carry out the task provided, which is further not dependable and leads to insufficient residual estimate of the unorganised sector. One of the major reasons behind these issues is the diversification of unorganised sector, where there is plethora of employment with different nature covered in this sector. As far as the permanent nature of the employment is concerned, the employment in organised sector is being casualised and are bound with various contracts over a period of time as a result of new economic and economic policies which are introduced these days. Furthermore, the workers in unorganised sector would eventually comprise of entire workforce of unorganised sector as well as the casual and contract workers in the organised sector, who somehow are not able to enjoy the legislations of benefits to the workers and social security umbrella guaranteed by these laws.

In addition, the workers who are directly or indirectly dependent on open natural resources which can also be covered under the ambit of public property are also an impeccable part of unorganised sector. Therefore, the

form of employment or labour relationship can be regarded as deciding factor to demarcate between the two sectors. But most of the time, the principal employer is absent due to which the conventional labour laws face difficulty in defining the casual and contractual workers as employees. The home worker or self-employed fall in grey area as there is no wage system and informal employee-employer relationship, but the ILO Convention Concerning Home Worker mentions that recommendations issued by various international labour conventions regarding the working conditions of the workforce are also applicable to the home worker as well.

CROWD-WORK ECONOMY – GIG WORKERS

The emergence of the gig workers in the economy is a direct result of “sharing” or “on-demand” economy due to constant shift from formal and traditional method of employment to the informal instinct of employment. The nature of work in which the gig workers are usually employed is more casual and temporary, where “Crowd-work” and “On-Demand work via App” are considered to be two major sources for the employment of these workers.

Due to rapid advancement in technology, most of the employment in this field is done through the online medium, which makes it easier for the employer to connect with the employees as well as clients at the global level. Therefore, in this case, most of the work is through App, where a firm controls the inflow of work to be assigned to the labours and the quality of services hereby bestowed by the workers. The best example for this form of employment is clearly the services provided by the Ola and Uber, where they hire various drivers in order to run their services. Moreover, in the year 2015, ILO conducted a survey where it was found that these firms contribute less than 10% of income generated for the maintenance of social security of its workers.

In September 2020, the strike broke out of the gig workers initiated by the Swiggy workers, who constantly claimed working for 15 hours a day and their salary was struck down from Rs. 20,000 to Rs. 5,000 despite of the fact that in 2020, the revenue of Swiggy was increased up to 127.8 percent. But this strike was not fruitful as in order to available the benefits of the legislations, it is important for the workers to be qualified as employee, which was not there at that point of time. As a result, this issue again is solved by the Social Security Code, as it clearly defines the term of gig workers under Section 2(35) of the respective Code.

However, the “Crowd-Work” economy is blooming with every single day and the key factors for this remains the constant evolution of technology and easy as well as remote connectivity. The nature of flexibility in nature of employment which gig economy can be qualified to be a three-fold system, wherein, at the side of employer, he can avail the services of the worker when required and the rigid salary system can be subsided which makes it cost-effective, while on the other side, the workers can provide their service at their own leisure and are not bound by one single employment perspective. Here, for the customer, it becomes more feasible and flexible to avail these services at their fingertips.

Gig Workers and Indian Economy

With the subsistent problem of huge population resulting in demographic dividend, the Indian economy has always faced the issue of unemployment due to various reasons, one of them being lack of skills required to be employed in the sophisticated sectors. But with the evolution of the concept of gig workers in India, it was considered as a ray of hope as the demand started to increase in this sector, where it was estimated that 3 million of employment was generated alone in India. In addition to this, the Chambers of Commerce in India also predicted that the employment through gig workers will increase by 17% annually by the target year of 2023. Though the concept of on-demand workers is unveiling its layers slowly in India, but it has been found that India is second largest hub of freelancers after USA. It is also predicted that with the constant and rapid change, the 50% of workforce would be freelancers in India and all of them being in the age group of 21-39 years. Nevertheless, it is apposite to understand that the gig system has somehow increased the participation of the people due to less or negligible restrictions imposed for the entry of the workers. Therefore, it is this steep but gradual increase guided the legislators to include the platform and gig workers in the Social Security Code.

Tryst of Gig Workers with Social Security Code

The concept of social security is not something which emerged with the Code itself, but it was there in various theories as well as reflected through various enactments, one of them being the Unorganised Workers’ Social Security Act, 2008 which took care of granting benefits to the workers of unorganised sector. In retrospective view, the major difference between the Act which came in 2008 and the umbrella like Social Security Code is that the Act was only confined to the unorganised workers, whereas, the Code initiated the inclusion of platform

and gig workers as a part of unorganised sector. With due research, it has been speculated that these platform and gig workers were also made entitled to the rights of Social Security was majorly due to the increase in the employment in these respective areas.

- **Environment before the Introduction of the Code**

Additionally, the Code simplified and rationalised other nine central legislations relating to welfare of the workers as well. The Social Security Act of 2008 lacked the provisions relating to the punishment for non-performance of administration, which again was solved by the Code wherein, it added Chapter XII which were related to the penal provisions. In order to substantiate, it has specifically penalised the act of deductions being made for the employer's contribution from the employee's salary or payment. Therefore, the mere recognition provided by the Code does not shield the workers from any sort of threat.

As in the case of *Ayantika Mondal v. State of Karnataka*, it was seen that merely because there was no backing of legislative enactment enacted by the State government for the protection of gig workers, the High Court was constrained from dismissing the writ petition filed therein. Practically, more than 90% of the workforce hail from the unorganised sector and thus are not able to avail the benefits of the legislation, for the matter of fact, the definitions provided under the Section 2(n) and Section 2(m) of the Unorganised Workers' Social Security Act, were restrictive in nature and thus does not include the protection of gig workers.

Within the ambit of Schedule I of the Act, several schemes were introduced for the welfare of the unorganised workers but it is ambiguous to determine whether it reached the targeted mass or not.

- **Environment after the Introduction of the Code**

The Code not only recognised but also defined the gig workers, as well as defined the term of platform workers separately, where it has been stated these are those workers who are engaged in specific works through online platform. Apart from these, the Code identifies other grouping of workers as well, such as contractors, dock workers, home based workers, unorganised workers and wage workers, etc. and the Code also ensures that the National Social Security Board provides various schemes and plans according to different strata of gig workers.

The Code directs the Central government to curate schemes for maintaining the interest of gig workers and provide substantial aid to their families as well, by establishment of Social Security Funds. The key factor which made the Code to stand out as new ray for the rights of unorganised sector is mentioned under Chapter IX of the Code, where it talks about the establishment of helpline by Central government, which will deal with queries regarding in order to facilitate the social schemes, registration and for the enrolment of registered gig workers in the prevailing social schemes. Furthermore, in order to avail these schemes, the gig workers under this Code needs to be registered, for the purpose of which, one must have:

- The age should be in between 16 years to 60 years
- Have provided Self-Declaration
- Have the possession of Aadhar Card
- These workers should have worked for at least 90 days for last 12 years

Platform Workers under the Ambit of Social Security Code

The emergence of platform workers is the result of steady technological developments which took place with the increase in cultural as well as economical flow throughout the world. These workers are those which perform specific tasks through online platform. The provisions provided under this Code which are applicable for the gig workers will as it is comply with the platform workers. These platform workers are mainly engaged in providing services to the customers through apps, being categorized as intermediaries and the employers will contact whenever their services are demanded.

Shortcomings of the Social Security Code

From the mere glance at the definition of gig workers, it can be traced that it talks about nature of employment where the work is considered to be outside the purview of employer-employee relationship. It however means that the employer and employee are independent of each other and the relation is time bound, where it is only limited to course of service bestowed to the customer through the employer. But the loopholes which is overlooked many times is that the Code remains silent on the nature of traditional employer-employee relationship. The Code also does not include the agricultural workers, street vendors and domestic workers.

The administration of National Social Security Board remains in question as the final discretion remains in the hands of Central government so identify and implement those schemes related to welfare of gig workers. Even

with the implementation of helpline numbers for the aid of gig workers, the registered gig workers have the mandatory compliance to update the address and identity of the workers but the ambiguity remains the same for those workers who do not have any idea regarding the registration and other processes.

Conclusion

The Indian labour legislations, prior to the Social Security Code, used to take various tests for establishing a person as an employee, such as the relationship with the employer, hiring technique and nature of the work, etc. The flexibility of these kinds of works has resulted in the increased participation of platform and gig workers, and it also targets various persons to get engaged in the delivering of services but at the same time it leads to the lack of formal service providers. Moreover, as there is an increase in online platforms subsequently it leads to lack of collective bargaining in the economy.

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- See <https://theguardian.com/an-analysis-on-gig-and-platform-workers-code-on-social-security/>, visited site on 26.03.2022 at 1500 IST.
- Section 2(78) of the defines social security as the measures of protection afforded to employees, unorganised workers, gig workers and platform workers to ensure access to health care and to provide income security, particularly in cases of old age, unemployment, sickness, invalidity, work injury, maternity or loss of a breadwinner by means of rights conferred on them and schemes framed, under this Code.
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- "wage worker" means a person employed for remuneration in the unorganised sector, directly by an employer or through any contractor, irrespective of place of work, whether exclusively for one employer or for one or more employers, whether in cash or in kind, whether as a home-based worker, or as a temporary or casual worker, or as a migrant worker, or workers employed by households including domestic workers, with a monthly wage of an amount as may be notified by the Central Government and State Government, as the case may be.
- "unorganised worker" means a home-based worker, self-employed worker or a wage worker in the unorganised sector and includes a worker in the organised sector who is not covered by any of the Acts mentioned in Schedule II to this Act.
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